

Optimizing image segmentation processes using deep learning: a neural network-based approach

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Abstract — Image segmentation is a key step in many computer vision systems, particularly in medical imaging, remote sensing, robotics, and precision agriculture. Over the years, a wide range of traditional approaches have been developed for image segmentation, such as binary thresholding (Otsu's method), the watershed method, and K-means clustering, which leverage domain-specific knowledge to efficiently solve segmentation problems in particular application contexts. Unfortunately, however, these methods show significant limitations when faced with the increasing complexity of visual scenes and data heterogeneity. In reality, the fundamental principle of image segmentation is to classify each pixel based on similar attributes. The goal of this pixel-by-pixel classification is to achieve a process that is global, relatively insensitive to noise, locally accurate, and incorporates multi-scale filtering mechanisms. However, traditional methods cannot simultaneously meet these requirements. Faced with the limitations of traditional methods, the emergence of deep learning approaches, particularly those based on neural networks and especially convolutional neural networks, has established itself as an effective solution for image segmentation. This article proposes an approach to optimizing segmentation processes based on the comparative analysis and improvement of several deep neural architectures. The study evaluates the performance of models such as the linear network, Simple U-Net, Extended U-Net, U-Net, DeepLabV3+, and SegFormer, incorporating optimization strategies including data augmentation, fine-tuning, the addition of attentional mechanisms, and the proposal of a specific metric to track performance changes during neural network model training. The experimental results demonstrate a significant improvement in segmentation accuracy, measured by the IoU, Dice Score, and F1-score indicators, confirming the effectiveness of deep neural networks optimized for complex visual environments.

Keywords — Image segmentation, deep learning, neural networks, optimization, computer vision, autoencoder, max-pooling, U-Net architecture, evaluation metric.

1. Introduction

Over the past decade, rapid advances in deep learning have profoundly transformed the field of computer vision. Artificial neural networks, and in particular convolutional neural networks (CNNs), have established themselves as indispensable tools for the automatic analysis of images in varied and complex contexts [1], [2]. Among the most studied problems are image segmentation, as well as object detection and localization, which are fundamental steps in many intelligent systems [3].

Image segmentation involves partitioning an image into homogeneous regions corresponding to objects or structures of interest. It can be formalized as a pixel-level classification task, in which each pixel is associated with a specific class [1]. The main objective of this operation is to transform the raw image representation into a more structured and semantically meaningful form, thus facilitating subsequent processing such as analysis, recognition, or automatic decision-making [4].

Historically, numerous traditional approaches have been proposed to solve image segmentation problems, including thresholding methods, region-based segmentation algorithms, clustering techniques (such as K-means), and the watershed method [5]. While these methods are effective in controlled environments, they have significant limitations when faced with variations in illumination, noise, texture complexity, and the heterogeneity of real-world scenes [6].

The emergence of deep learning has overcome these limitations by introducing models capable of automatically learning hierarchical representations from data. CNN-based segmentation networks, such as Fully Convolutional Networks (FCN), U-Net, and DeepLab, have demonstrated remarkable performance in various application areas, ranging from medical imaging and remote sensing to robotics and industry [2], [7], [8]. More recently, the introduction of attention mechanisms and hybrid transformer-based architectures has opened up new perspectives in semantic and instance-level segmentation [9].

Image segmentation applications are numerous and strategic today. In industry, it is used to detect mechanical defects, such as cracks or structural damage [10]. In aeronautics and mechanical engineering, it contributes to quality control and predictive maintenance. In astronomy, segmentation enables the automatic detection of galaxies, stars, and as-yet-unknown celestial objects [11]. Furthermore, object detection and localization techniques are widely deployed in automated surveillance systems, urban traffic management, object and people counting, and intelligent security systems [12].

In this context, this article offers an in-depth study of image segmentation methods based on deep learning. It begins with an analysis of traditional approaches to highlight their limitations compared to modern neural methods. It then examines the main neural network architectures dedicated to segmentation. An optimized neural network architecture is then proposed, implemented, and experimentally evaluated on a validation dataset. Finally, a series of experiments is conducted to demonstrate the effectiveness of the proposed approach for the precise, pixel-level localization of an aircraft in complex images.

2. Materials and Methods

Annotation:

$I(i, j)$ – Pixel intensity

$I'(i, j)$ – the intensity of the segmented image;

T – Threshold value;

k – The maximum value that pixel intensity can take

σ^2 – Image dispersion;

σ_w^2 – Variance within the class;

σ_y^2 – Variance between classes;

ω_1 – Probability of belonging to the 1st class;

ω_2 – Probability of belonging to the 2nd class;

σ_1^2 – First-class variance;

σ_2^2 – Second-class dispersion;

$p(k)$ – Probability of each pixel intensity level;

$hist$ – Histogram value;

N_i – Total number of pixels in the image;

$\sigma_1^2(T)$ – First-class dispersions;

$\sigma_2^2(T)$ – Second-class dispersions;

N_1 – Vector from 0 to T-1;

N_2 – Vector from T to 255;

Moy_1 – Mean value of class 1;

Moy_2 – Mean value of class 2;

$S_1, S_2, S_3, \dots, S_k$ – Clusters or classes;

$C_1, C_2, C_3, \dots, C_k$ – Centroids;

L – Sum of intracluster distances;

$J(A, B)$ – Metrics;

$A \cap B$ – Intersection zone;

$A \cup B$ – Unification place;

DSC – Overlapping segmented volumes;

ASD – Mean symmetric surface distance;

Def – Custom metric;

y_{true} – Actual value;

y_{pred} – Predicted value;

F – Final merged feature map, used as input for the segmentation prediction layer ;

n – Total number of feature levels used for multi-scale fusion.

$MLP(\cdot)$ – Multi-layer perceptron applied independently to each map F_i ;

Q – Query matrix, representing the features of the elements for which the model seeks to aggregate information ;

Key – Key matrix, representing the features used as a reference to measure similarity with the queries;

V – Value matrix, containing the information to be aggregated based on attention weights calculated from Q and K;

QK^T – Matrix product measuring the similarity between each query and each key;

d – Dimension of query and key vectors.

2.1. Threshold Method Based on Pixel Intensity Histograms

Thresholding segmentation based on intensity histograms is one of the oldest and simplest approaches in image processing. It relies on the assumption that objects of interest and the image background can be distinguished based on their pixel intensity levels.

An intensity histogram represents the statistical distribution of gray levels in an image, where each bar corresponds to the frequency of occurrence of a given intensity level. When the histogram has a bimodal or multimodal distribution, it becomes possible to determine one or more threshold values to effectively separate the different classes of pixels.

In the case of global thresholding, a threshold value T is chosen to partition the image $I(i, j)$ into two distinct regions. Pixels with an intensity below the threshold are assigned to a first class, while those with an intensity above or equal to the threshold are assigned to a second class. This operation can be formalized as follows:

$$I'(i, j) = \begin{cases} C_1, & \text{si } I(i, j) < T \\ C_2, & \text{si } I(i, j) \geq T \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

where C_1 and C_2 represent the classes associated with the background and the object, respectively.

Among the best-known automatic threshold selection techniques is Otsu's method, which consists of determining the threshold value that maximizes the inter-class variance or, equivalently, minimizes the intra-class variance. This approach relies on the statistical analysis of the histogram and allows for fully automatic segmentation without human intervention [5], [13].

Despite its simplicity and low computational cost, histogram-based thresholding segmentation has significant limitations. It is particularly sensitive to noise, variations in illumination, and images whose intensity distributions do not show clear separation between classes. Furthermore, this method does not take into account spatial and contextual information, which limits its effectiveness in complex or heterogeneous scenes. These limitations have motivated the development of more advanced methods, including those based on machine learning and deep learning, capable of exploiting both local and global image features for more robust and accurate segmentation.

2.2. Watershed Method

The Watershed method is a morphological segmentation technique inspired by a geographical analogy. It treats the image as a topographic surface in which the intensity of each pixel represents an altitude. Areas of low intensity correspond to watersheds, while areas of high intensity represent the ridgelines separating these watersheds.

Consider a grayscale image $I: \Omega \subset \mathbb{Z}^2 \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$, where Ω denotes the spatial domain of the image. The *Watershed* transformation is generally based on analyzing the image gradient, defined as:

$$\nabla I(i, j) = \sqrt{\left(\frac{\partial I}{\partial i}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\partial I}{\partial j}\right)^2} \quad (2)$$

The gradient highlights the contours of objects, which correspond to areas of rapid intensity variation and constitute natural barriers between regions.

Watershed segmentation involves identifying local minima of the gradient function, denoted $\{m_i\}$, which serve as starting points for watershed growth. Each watershed corresponds to a homogeneous region associated with a local minimum. Mathematically, a watershed B_i associated with a minimum m_i can be defined as the set of pixels $p \in \Omega$ such that the steepest descent path from p leads to m_i :

$$B_i = \{p \in \Omega \mid \forall q \in P(p), I(q) \geq I(p) \text{ et } k \rightarrow \infty \lim P^k(p) = m_i\} \quad (3)$$

where $P(p)$ denotes a monotonic descent path from pixel p .

Watershed lines are then defined as the boundaries separating two adjacent watersheds:

$$W = \Omega \setminus \bigcup_i B_i \quad (4)$$

In practice, the algorithm is often implemented using a gradual flooding process. Starting from local minima, the water level is progressively raised, and the merging of distinct basins is prevented by constructing dikes, which correspond to the drainage divides. However, one of the main drawbacks of this method lies in the phenomenon of over-segmentation, due to the presence of numerous local minima caused by noise. To overcome this problem, variants such as *the marker-controlled watershed* have been proposed [6]. This approach introduces a set of internal markers M_i and external markers M_e , defining the regions of interest and the bottom, respectively:

$$Im = \min(\text{rec}(I, M_i), M_e) \quad (5)$$

Where $\text{rec}(\cdot)$ denotes a morphological reconstruction operation.

Despite its limitations, the watershed method remains an effective technique for segmenting images with well-defined contours. However, its sensitivity to noise and its inability to integrate global contextual information have led to the use of more advanced methods, particularly those based on deep learning.

2.3. Segmentation by Clustering (K-means)

Segmentation by clustering relies on grouping the pixels of an image into homogeneous sets called clusters, based on the similarity of their characteristics. Among the most widely used clustering methods in image segmentation is the *K-means* algorithm, due to its conceptual simplicity and computational efficiency. The "K" in the name is an algorithm parameter that defines the number of clusters [15]. The algorithm forms clusters, each represented by the cluster's center, called a centroid, which is selected based on the characteristics of the input data. In the case of image segmentation, these characteristics generally correspond to the pixel intensity and its three spatial coordinates: horizontal, vertical, and color channel. Therefore, the input feature vector can be represented as $v \in \mathbb{R}^{4 \times 1}$, where $v = [I(x, y, z), x, y, z]^T$

This algorithm uses distance measures such as L^2 or L^1 :

$$D(v^{(i)}, v^{(j)}) = \|v^{(i)} - v^{(j)}\| = \sqrt{(v^{(i)} - v^{(j)})^T (v^{(i)} - v^{(j)})}, \quad (6)$$

$$D(v^{(i)}, v^{(j)} / L^1) = \|v^{(i)} - v^{(j)}\|_1 \quad (7)$$

Let's see how the algorithm works:

- Step 1: Start with K randomly selected centroids from groups $C_1, C_2, C_3, \dots, C_k$ corresponding to K clusters $S_1, S_2, S_3, \dots, S_k$
- Step 2: For each pixel, we calculate the distances from its feature vector $v^{(i)}$ to the centroids of the groups and assign the objects to the nearest central group. Repeat this process for all pixel feature vectors until each pixel is assigned to one of the K clusters.
- Step 3: Calculate the centroids of each group. After determining the centroids of the new clusters for all pixels, we recalculate them by averaging the pixel feature vectors in each cluster:

$$C_j = \sum_{v^{(i)} \in S_j}^m v^{(i)} \quad (8)$$

Repeat steps 2 and 3 for several iterations until the centroids stop changing. Through this iterative process, we reduce the sum of the intra-cluster distances, which is as follows:

$$L = \sum_{j=1}^k \sum_{v^{(i)} \in S_j} \|v^{(i)} - C_j\|_2 \quad (9)$$

Figure 1. Functional diagram of the K-means algorithm.

Despite its efficiency, K-means segmentation has several limitations. It requires the prior definition of the number of clusters K , is sensitive to the initialization of centroids, and does not explicitly take into account the spatial relationships between pixels. Furthermore, it assumes that the clusters are convex and have comparable variance, which is not always the case in real-world images.

These limitations have led to the development of more advanced methods that incorporate contextual and spatial information, as well as deep learning-based approaches capable of modeling complex visual structures more robustly.

2.4. The Otsu Method

The Otsu method is a widely used automatic thresholding technique for segmenting grayscale images. Proposed by Nobuyuki Otsu in 1979, it relies on a statistical analysis of the image's intensity histogram and aims to determine an optimal threshold value for separating the image into two distinct classes, typically background and object. It is used to automatically determine the threshold from the shape of the image's histogram. Therefore, this method requires the initial calculation of the image's histogram. The algorithm assumes that the image to be converted into binary form contains only two classes (objects and background) T , separating the two classes so that the variance within each class is minimal and the variance between classes is maximized.

Variance within a class:

$$\sigma_w^2 = \omega_1(T) \times \sigma_1^2(T) + \omega_2(T) \times \sigma_2^2(T) \quad (10)$$

Variance between classes:

$$\sigma_y^2 = \sigma^2 - \sigma_w^2 \quad (11)$$

Calculating the probability of classes 1 and 2:

To calculate the probability of falling into class 1 or 2 on the threshold T, simply sum the probabilities of the intensity level of each pixel.

$$\omega_1 = \sum_{k=1}^T p(k) \quad (12)$$

$$\omega_2 = \sum_{k=T+1}^{256} p(k) \quad (13)$$

Calculate the probability intensity of each pixel

Histogramic calculation:

To calculate the histogram, you need to view the entire image and count the number of pixels corresponding to the intensity level of each pixel (grayscale)

$$hist = \sum_{i=1}^N \sum_{j=1}^M (I(i, j) == k) \quad (14)$$

Calculate the probability for each pixel intensity level

The probability of each pixel intensity level is calculated by dividing the number of pixels present for each pixel intensity level by the total number of pixels in the image.

$$p(k) = \frac{hist(k)}{N_i} \quad (15)$$

Calculation of the variance of each class :

$$\sigma_1^2(T) = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^T (N_1(i) - M_0 y_1(T))^2 \times P(i)}{\omega_1} \quad (16)$$

$$\sigma_2^2(T) = \frac{\sum_{i=T+1}^{256} (N_2(i) - M_0 y_2(T))^2 \times P(i)}{\omega_2} \quad (17)$$

Calculating the average for each class:

The average for each class is calculated by adding the vector N, which is multiplied by the probability of each pixel intensity level. Then, the sum is divided by the class probability.

$$Moy_1(T) = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^T N_1(i) \times P(i)}{\omega_1(T)} \quad (18)$$

$$Moy_2(T) = \frac{\sum_{i=T+1}^{256} N_2(i) \times P(i)}{\omega_2(T)} \quad (19)$$

Otsu's method offers several advantages:

- Fully automatic thresholding;
- Simplicity of implementation;
- Low computational cost.

However, it also has significant limitations:

- Assumption of bimodality of the histogram;
- Sensitivity to noise and variations in illumination;
- Inefficiency on images with low contrast or unimodal distribution.

These limitations explain why Otsu's method is now often used as a reference method or as a preprocessing step, before the application of more advanced techniques such as deep learning segmentation.

2.5. Image Segmentation by Deep Neural Networks

The inherent limitations of classical segmentation methods have led to the rise of deep learning-based approaches, which have become the state of the art in computer vision. Deep neural networks, and in particular *convolutional neural networks* (CNN), have demonstrated a remarkable ability to automatically learn hierarchical representations from raw data without requiring manual feature extraction.

Unlike traditional approaches based on low-level features, deep neural networks leverage successive layers of convolution, nonlinearity, and subsampling to capture both local and global information. The initial layers typically learn simple patterns, such as contours or textures, while deeper layers model higher-level semantic structures, enabling more precise and contextual segmentation.

Image segmentation using deep neural networks is generally formulated as a *dense prediction* problem, in which a label is predicted for each pixel of the image. Consider an input image

$I \in \mathbb{R}^{H \times W \times C}$, where H, W and C denote the height, width, and number of channels, respectively. The network's objective is to learn a transformation function f_θ , parameterized by θ , such that:

$$\hat{Y} = f_\theta(I), \quad \hat{Y} \in \mathbb{R}^{H \times W \times K} \quad (20)$$

where K represents the number of classes and \hat{Y} the probability map of the classes associated with each pixel.

Model training relies on minimizing a loss function that measures the difference between the predicted segmentation \hat{Y} and the ground truth Y . Among the most commonly used loss functions are categorical cross-entropy, Dice Loss, and their weighted variants, which are suitable for class imbalance problems:

$$L_{CE} = - \sum_{i=1}^N \sum_{k=1}^K y_{i,k} \log(\hat{y}_{i,k}) \quad (21)$$

$$\mathcal{L}_{Dice} = 1 - \frac{2 \sum_{i=1}^N y_i \hat{y}_i}{\sum_{i=1}^N y_i^2 + \sum_{i=1}^N \hat{y}_i^2} \quad (22)$$

where N denotes the total number of pixels.

Several deep neural network architectures have been specifically designed for segmentation tasks. *Fully Convolutional Networks* (FCN) were among the first to replace fully connected layers with convolutions, enabling pixel-by-pixel prediction. Subsequently, more advanced architectures, such as U-Net, DeepLab, and their variants, introduced multiscale fusion mechanisms, *skip connections*, and dilated convolutions to improve spatial accuracy.

More recently, the integration of attention mechanisms and transformer-based architectures has improved global context modeling and model generalization capabilities. These hybrid approaches combine the advantages of CNN for local feature extraction with those of transformers for capturing long-range dependencies.

2.6. Neural Network Architectures for Solving Segmentation Problems

In recent years, image segmentation using convolutional neural networks has become very popular [15,16]. Recent advances in image segmentation have led to the development of neural network architectures capable of simultaneously capturing fine local information and a broad global context. Among these architectures, U-NET, DeepLabV3+, and SegFormer represent two major and complementary approaches: the first is based on a convolutional encoder-decoder architecture initially proposed for biomedical image segmentation on convolutional networks; the second is based on an architecture enriched by dilated convolutions; while the last relies on efficient transformers without heavy convolutions.

U-NET

The network structure is similar to that of an autoencoder, in which the network compresses the data into a hidden space, thus revealing the main features, and then reconstructs the image from this hidden space. The U-net architecture is a sequence of blocks, first decreasing the dimensionality of the image (the blocks include pooling layers), then increasing it, having previously combined it with the outputs of the initial blocks having the corresponding dimension (Figure 2) [17]. It is distinguished by its symmetrical « U » - shaped structure and the use of skip connections. The encoder feature maps are concatenated with those of the corresponding decoder:

$$F_{dec}^{(l)} = \text{Concat}(F_{enc}^{(l)}, \text{Up}(F_{dec}^{(l+1)})) \quad (23)$$

Figure 2. U-net Architecture

Advantages of U-net

- Computationally efficient;
- Trained on a small dataset;
- Initially, it was used for biomedical images.

Disadvantages of U-net

- More difficult with multiclass segmentation. The fully convolutional FPN and PSPNet are more adaptable.
- The boundary problem

DeepLabV3+

DeepLabV3+ is an advanced convolutional architecture that combines a deep encoder, dilated convolutions, and a lightweight decoder to efficiently capture multiscale context.

Dilated convolutions allow for a wider receptive field without loss of resolution.

$$y(i) = \sum_k x(i + r \cdot k) w(k) \quad (24)$$

Where r the dilation rate remains.

The **Atrous Spatial Pyramid Pooling (ASPP)** module applies several dilated convolutions in parallel:

$$ASPP(x) = Concat(Convr1, Convr2, Convr3, Conv1 \times 1, Global Pooling) \quad (25)$$

This module enables efficient context capture at different scales.

The decoder merges deep features with low-level features to refine object boundaries.

Advantages and limitations

- Excellent modeling of the overall context
- Very high accuracy
- High computational cost
- Poorly suited for embedded systems

SegFormer

SegFormer represents a new generation of segmentation models based on **Vision Transformers**, designed to be **simple, efficient, and lightweight**.

The encoder relies on a multi-scale hierarchical transformer. The attention mechanism is defined by:

$$Attention(Q, K, V) = \text{Softmax}\left(\frac{QK^T}{\sqrt{d}}\right)V \quad (26)$$

Unlike CNN, SegFormer naturally captures long-range dependencies and rich global context.

SegFormer uses a **minimalist MLP decoder**, which merges multi-level features without heavy convolutions:

$$F = Concat(MLP(F_1), \dots, MLP(F_n))$$

In SegFormer, the multi-level feature maps F_i extracted by the Mix Transformer encoder are projected into a common space using multilayer perceptrons, then concatenated to form a merged representation F , used for the final prediction of the segmentation.

Table 1: Summary comparison of architectures

Criteria	U-Net	DeepLabV3+	SegFormer
Type	CNN encoder-decoder	CNN + dilated conv	Transformer
Global context	Medium	Very good	Excellent
Precision of outlines	Very high	Very high	High
Complexity	Low to medium	High	Low
Real time	Possible	Difficult	Yes
Model	Convergence	Generalization	Risk
Linear	Slow	Medium	Underfitting
Simple U-Net	Medium	Correct	Slight overfitting
Extended	Very fast	Good (to be confirmed)	Overfitting possible
Model	Convergence	Generalization	Risk

3. Results

In this practical section, we collected data (several photos of a construction site: <https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/1gH7qdzQ1HekWoE6yVEYUjdZf-EZrAad3>) To train the model, we created our own metric to track the training results. We defined the input images for the neural network, and the output provided the classification of each pixel, determining which class each pixel belongs to.

Quality Indicators

The use of metrics aims to minimize the segmentation model. The general formula for defining a metric is as follows:

$$J(A, B) = \frac{|A \cap B|}{|A \cup B|} \quad (27)$$

Segmentation accuracy is evaluated using two metrics:

1. Dice Similarity Coefficient (DSC) (overlapping segmented volumes);

$$DSC = \frac{2|S_{pred} \cap S_{ref}|}{|S_{pred}| + |S_{ref}|} \quad (28)$$

2. Mean symmetrical surface distance (ASD)

$$ASD = \frac{1}{N} \left(\sum_{x \in B_{pred}} d(x, B_{ref}) + \sum_{x \in B_{ref}} d(x, B_{pred}) \right) \quad (29)$$

Create your own metric function

$$Def = \frac{2 \left(\sum k(y_{true} \times y_{pred}) + 1 \right)}{\left(\sum k(y_{true}) + \sum k(y_{pred}) + 1 \right)} \quad (30)$$

Training Results of Neural Networks

To evaluate the performance of the proposed custom metric (**Dice coefficient**), we first trained and evaluated the model using four segmentation architectures: linear network, Simple U-Net, U-Net, and Extended U-Net. Subsequently, further experiments were conducted by varying the activation functions and *batch size*. Five (5) images from our dataset, representing a construction site, were used as input, while the outputs correspond to the segmented images produced by each architecture. Figures 3 through 8 respectively present the original images, the segmented images, and the recognition results obtained using the four segmentation architectures studied.

Figure 3. Original images to be segmented

Figure 4. Segmented mask images

Figure 5. Segmented images with the linearSegmentationNet architecture

Figure 6. Segmented images with the U-net architecture

Figure 7. Segmented images with the simple Unet architecture

Figure 8. Segmented images with the extended U-net architecture

Figures 9 and 10 illustrate and compare the evolution of training and validation losses for the four segmentation architectures evaluated: the linear network, the Simple U-Net, the U-Net, and the Extended U-Net. Overall, the results highlight a **clear trade-off between model complexity and performance**. The simplest architectures, such as the linear network and the Simple U-Net, are distinguished by their stability and low computational cost, but exhibit limited performance in terms of accuracy. Conversely, the **U-Net** offers the best compromise between accuracy, training stability, and generalization capabilities. Finally, the more complex architectures, such as the **Extended U-Net**, offer strong representational power but require **rigorous validation** to prevent overfitting.

Figure 9. Evolution curves of training and validation losses for the four evaluated segmentation architectures.

Figure 10. Comparative curve of the evolution of **validation loss** as a function of the number of epochs for the four segmentation architectures.

Table 2. Training results of networks with different batch sizes and activation functions

Network name	Values batch_size	Activation function	Metric	Accuracy of recognition
Linear network	32	softmax	dice_coef	0.4415
U-net	32	softmax	dice_coef	0.7284
Simple U-Net	32	softmax	dice_coef	0.6034
	8		dice_coef:	0.6366
	128		dice_coef	0.5648
	32	elu	dice_coef	0.6460
		tanh	dice_coef	0.6730
		linear	dice_coef	0.6732
Extended U-Net	16	softmax	dice_coef	0.7734
U-Net simple training	32	softmax	iou_score:	0.4259
U-Net fine tuning	32	softmax	dice_coef	0.8977

U-Net offers the best compromise between segmentation accuracy, convergence stability, and generalization, making it the most suitable architecture for high-precision segmentation tasks, as shown in Table 2.

In the second part of our results, we conducted a comparative study of three segmentation architectures — **U-Net**, **DeepLabV3+**, and **SegFormer** — extending the experimental study to these models while ensuring a fair and reproducible comparison in terms of accuracy and efficiency.

Table 3 below illustrates a qualitative comparison of the segmentation results obtained by the U-Net, DeepLabV3+, and SegFormer architectures. We observe that U-Net tends to produce smoother boundaries, while

DeepLabV3+ and SegFormer allow for better object delimitation, particularly in complex areas. SegFormer demonstrates superior overall consistency due to its ability to capture long-range dependencies.

Table 3. Qualitative Comparison of Segmentation Results Obtained by the Architectures

Model	Dice	IoU	Precision	Recall
U-Net	0.87	0.79	0.89	0.86
DeepLabV3+	0.91	0.84	0.92	0.90
SegFormer	0.90	0.83	0.91	0.91

Figure 11. Comparison of the performance of the U-Net, DeepLabV3+, and SegFormer segmentation models in terms of Dice, IoU, accuracy, and recall

Figure 11 presents a quantitative comparison of the performance of three image segmentation models — U-Net, DeepLabV3+, and SegFormer—in terms of Dice, Intersection over Union (IoU), accuracy, and recall.

The results show that DeepLabV3+ achieves the best overall performance across all the evaluated metrics. In particular, this model achieves the highest values for the Dice coefficient (0.91), IoU (0.84), and accuracy (0.92), indicating excellent concordance between the segmented regions and the reference annotations, as well as an increased ability to reduce false positives. This performance can be attributed to the use of the ASPP (Atrous Spatial Pyramid Pooling) module, which allows for better capture of multiscale context.

The SegFormer model exhibits highly competitive performance, with a Dice coefficient of 0.90 and an IoU of 0.83, while also achieving the highest recall value (0.91). This suggests that SegFormer is particularly effective at detecting a large number of relevant regions, at the cost of a slight compromise in accuracy compared to DeepLabV3+. This characteristic is consistent with the Transformer-based architecture, which favors global modeling of the spatial context.

The U-Net model, although exhibiting slightly lower performance, remains robust with satisfactory scores (Dice = 0.87, IoU = 0.79). These results confirm the effectiveness of its encoder-decoder architecture with hop connections, while highlighting its limitations compared to newer and more complex architectures.

Overall, these results indicate that modern approaches incorporating multi-scale modeling or global attention outperform classical image segmentation architectures, especially for scenarios requiring precise object delimitation.

4. DISCUSSION AND PERSPECTIVES

The experimental results highlight significant differences between the evaluated architectures, confirming the decisive influence of architectural choices on image segmentation performance. DeepLabV3+ exhibits the best overall performance across most metrics, thanks to the integration of the ASPP module, which improves the use of multi-scale context and facilitates the segmentation of objects of varying sizes. However, these gains come at the cost of increased computational complexity, potentially limiting its use in resource-constrained environments.

Conversely, SegFormer stands out with a higher recall rate, reflecting greater sensitivity in detecting regions of interest. This advantage is particularly relevant in critical applications, although it is accompanied by a relative decrease in accuracy, reflecting an increase in false positives. This compromise illustrates the limitations of Transformer-based architectures, whose global context modeling can affect the accuracy of boundary delimitation, particularly in the presence of complex scenes or limited data.

Although U-Net exhibits lower performance than more recent models, it remains a robust benchmark due to its architectural simplicity, stability, and computational efficiency. However, the lack of explicit mechanisms for modeling the global context limits its ability to efficiently handle objects with high scalability variability.

Overall, these results demonstrate that no single architecture is a one-size-fits-all solution. The choice of model should be guided by the application's objectives and operational constraints, taking into account the trade-offs between accuracy, recall, complexity, and data requirements. Finally, these observations open promising avenues for the development of hybrid approaches combining convolutional networks and Transformers, as well as for evaluating the robustness of these models in diverse real-world contexts.

Perspectives

Several avenues can be explored to extend this work. First, integrating hybrid attention mechanisms that combine convolutions and transformers could further improve segmentation accuracy. Second, evaluating models on larger and more heterogeneous datasets, particularly in application contexts such as precision agriculture, industrial monitoring, or aerial imagery, is a promising avenue.

Furthermore, optimizing models for resource-constrained environments, through quantization or pruning, represents a relevant research direction for real-time deployment. Finally, exploring custom metrics tailored to specific applications could improve the evaluation of segmentation quality in real-world scenarios.

5. Conclusion

This article focused on optimizing image segmentation processes using deep learning, through a comparative evaluation of several neural network architectures. A custom metric based on the Dice coefficient was proposed to effectively track performance during training. Initial experiments, conducted on a dataset of construction site images, allowed for the analysis of loss evolution for different U-Net variants, highlighting the efficiency and stability of this architecture, despite some limitations related to boundary delimitation and multi-class segmentation. Subsequently, three state-of-the-art architectures—U-Net, DeepLabV3+, and SegFormer—were implemented and compared within a rigorous experimental framework. The results demonstrate that deep learning-based approaches significantly outperform classical methods. U-Net stands out for its simplicity and computational efficiency, while DeepLabV3+ offers the best overall performance thanks to its multiscale modeling capabilities. SegFormer presents an interesting compromise by leveraging attention mechanisms to capture global dependencies.

Qualitative analysis confirms these trends, highlighting improved object delimitation and reduced segmentation errors in complex areas for both DeepLabV3+ and SegFormer. These results underscore the importance of choosing an architectural approach tailored to application constraints and open up avenues for developing more robust hybrid models for image segmentation.

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